

RESULTS OF ECHOGRAPHIC STUDY OF KIDNEY BIOMETRIC INDICATORS AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE

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Abstract. *Modern nephrology has accumulated a sufficient body of knowledge about ultrasound methods, tomography of the kidneys, and other diagnostic techniques. However, there is still no comprehensive justification for the use of a particular method in specific nosological forms of the disease, nor are there unified adapted criteria for interpreting results. Most criteria for determining the severity and stage of chronic kidney disease (CKD) are based on clinical-laboratory diagnostic methods, which may not always provide reliable information. Moreover, non-invasive evaluations of kidney function, such as ultrasound imaging and intra-renal blood flow parameters, are not always performed by practicing physicians at different stages of CKD. Simultaneously, the progressive decline in kidney function, as well as many hidden renal and somatic disorders, remain unseen by doctors. Additionally, the number of patients with CKD continues to rise, which is largely due to the high incidence of pyelonephritis in our republic, especially in children and pregnant women, various nephropathies, urolithiasis, kidney developmental anomalies, and the addition of bacterial and fungal infections.*

Keywords: *chronic kidney disease (CKD), somatic disorders, kidney interstitium, histiolympocytic infiltrates.*

Objective of the study: To investigate the biometric indicators of kidneys at various stages of chronic kidney disease.

Material and Methods: As shown by the results of our previous studies, chronic kidney disease (CKD) often has a sluggish course without a period of sustained remission, with the disease continuing and gradually acquiring irreversible changes. We examined 203 patients, including 151 patients (56 men and 95 women) with various stages of CKD, aged 18 to 89 years, and 52 healthy individuals (13 men and 39 women) who made up the control group, aged 18 to 79 years. The age division was carried out according to the generally accepted scheme for the periodization of biological age in medicine, as established by the WHO (Issue No. 3, 2017). Analysis of age and sex distribution in the adult population revealed that CKD predominated in females, accounting for 63.0% (n=95). Based on the results of comprehensive examination, the patients in the main group were divided into four groups: Group I included 48 (31.8%) patients with CKD stages 1-2 (60-89 ml/min/1.73m²); Group II included 66 (43.7%) patients with CKD stage 3 (30 patients with stage 3A (45.4%) and 36 with stage 3B (54.6%)) (30-59 ml/min/1.73m²); Group III included 37 (24.5%) patients with CKD stages 4-5 (20 with stage 4 (54.0%) and 17 with stage 5 (end-stage renal disease, ESRD) (46.0%)) (<15-29 ml/min/1.73m²); Group IV (control group, n=52) consisted of healthy individuals with normal estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR >90).

Results of the Study: To assess kidney biometric indicators, special attention was given to symmetric changes in kidney size, thickness of the parenchymal and cortical layers, and their echogenicity. No significant differences were found between the physiological sizes of the left and

right kidneys at different stages of CKD. In cases where asymmetry in kidney size exceeding normal values was detected, those patients were excluded from the study. When studying the biometric sizes of the kidneys, we measured the length, width, and thickness in centimeters, calculated the kidney volume in sm^3 , and measured the cross-section of the pyramids in sm^2 . The results of the measurements of kidney biometric dimensions are presented in Table 1.

The presented data indicate a certain dynamic trend, with an observed increase in kidney size (length, width, thickness of the parenchyma and cortical layer) compared to the control group. An increase ($p < 0.05$) in these parameters was noted in patients with CKD stages 1 and 2, which, according to many researchers, is associated with hyperemia of the vascular bed, the presence of histio-lymphocytic infiltrates in the stroma, thickening of the mesangial matrix in glomeruli, edema, and inflammatory infiltration of the kidney interstitium, caused by the morphological activity of the underlying pathological process.

Table 1. Biometric Parameters of Kidney Size in Patients with Different Stages of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)

Biometric parameters of the kidney	Control n=52	Stages of CKD				
		Optimal	Moderate		Severe	ESRD
		Stages 1,2 n= 30	S 3A $\pi=30$	S 3B $\pi=30$	S4 $\pi=30$	S5 $\pi=30$
Kidney volume, sm^3	140,1± 5,7	168,4±14,06	169,3±12,61	169,6±12,44	148,4±18,62	94,9±9,51
Length cm^3	11,2± 0,41	12,6±0,62	12,4±0,66	12,1±0,56	11,1±0,11	9,1±0,33
Width, cm	5,3±0,12	5,8±0,44	5,9±0,42	5,8±0,44	5,1±0,41	4,6±0,33
Thickness, sm	4,9±0,23	5,1±0,29	5,2±0,31	4,8±0,42	4,7±0,46	4,1±0,21
Parenchyma	1,6±0,06	1,9±0,13	1,8±0,14	1,7±0,11	1,5±0,15	1,1±0,1
Cortex	0,71±0,03	0,89±0,6	0,84±0,04	0,81±0,03	0,68±0,08	0,48±0,08
Pyramid section, 2 sm	0,46±0,04	0,62±0,62	0,58±0,06	0,59±0,03	0,42±0,02	0,31±0,03

Note: The significance of the difference with the control group is $p < 0.001$.

At stages 3A and 3B of CKD, a statistically significant reduction in kidney biometric measurements is observed, particularly in the thickness of the parenchyma and the cortical layer, compared to stages 1 and 2 of CKD. These results suggest that at stage 3 of CKD, early signs of sclerotic changes occur, such as glomerulosclerosis, arteriosclerosis, with subsequent replacement of the parenchyma and cortical layer by fibrous tissue. This opinion is supported by many modern researchers.

This observation is confirmed by the results of clinical and functional studies of the kidneys. At this stage, the glomerular filtration rate decreases significantly to 30 ml/min, and serum creatinine and urea levels are significantly elevated. These changes allow for the detection of the initial clinical manifestations of chronic renal failure. In the case of terminal chronic renal failure, a statistically significant reduction in kidney biometric measurements ($p < 0.05$) is observed compared to the control group and stages of CKD with lighter severity.

Analysis of changes in kidney size, thickness of the parenchyma, and cortical layer, which are key features of nephrosclerosis, revealed certain patterns. At stages 1, 2, and 3 of CKD, these

parameters remained slightly increased compared to the control group. Comparison of these data with clinical and functional indicators and serum creatinine levels at stage 3B of CKD shows a significant decrease in glomerular filtration rate with moderate azotemia compared to stages 1 and 2 of CKD. This suggests that starting from stage 3B of CKD, there is an enhanced tendency towards nephrosclerosis, which requires intensifying the treatment approach. At stage 4 of CKD, the thickness of the parenchyma and the cortical layer tends to decrease compared to the control group and compared to stages 1, 2, 3A, and 3B of CKD. Comparison of ultrasound results and clinical-functional indicators of the kidneys demonstrates reliable signs of chronic renal failure.

A significant decrease in glomerular filtration rate (GFR 22.4 ± 6.2 ml/min) and an increase in creatinine levels (368.4 ± 21.8 μ mol/L) are observed, along with an increase in the frequency of arterial hypertension and the development of anemia syndrome (see Table 2).

In general, these data indicate the need for comprehensive treatment that includes active conservative methods as well as pathogenetic, cardio-nephroprotective, and anti-anemic therapies in the terminal stage of chronic kidney disease (CKD). Ultrasound results show a significant reduction in the thickness of the kidney parenchyma and cortical layer, accompanied by a decrease in linear kidney size, which reliably indicates signs of nephrosclerosis.

Table 2

Comparison of Biometric Data and Filtration Indicators at Different Stages of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)

Clinical and functional kidney dimensions	Stages of Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD)					
	control group n=30	Group 1 Stage 1,2 of CKD n=48	Group 2 Stage 3		Group 3	
			S3A n=30	S3B n=36	S4 n=20	ECKD C5 n=17
GFR ml/min	109 \pm 9,2	79,2 \pm 11,8	51,1 \pm 7,3	36,6 \pm 6,2	22,4 \pm 6,2	11,9 \pm 3,1
KR, %	99,0%	99,0%	97,8 \pm 0,6	97,1 \pm 1,1	96,2 \pm 1,8	95,9 \pm 1,9
Creatinine, ммол/л	67,6 \pm 18,6	84,0 \pm 24,2	146,4 \pm 9,2	213,3 \pm 7,3	368,4 \pm 21,8	668,4 \pm 26,6
Kidney volume, см ³	140,1 \pm 5,7	168,4 \pm 14,0	169,3 \pm 12,6	169,6 \pm 12,4	148,4 \pm 18,6	94,9 \pm 9,5
Length, sm	11,2 \pm 0,41	12,6 \pm 0,62	12,4 \pm 0,66	12,1 \pm 0,56	11,1 \pm 0,11	9,1 \pm 0,33
Width, sm	5,3 \pm 0,12	5,8 \pm ,44	5,9 \pm 0,42	5,8 \pm 0,44	5,1 \pm 0,41	4,6 \pm 0,33
Thickness, sm	4,9 \pm 0,23	5,1 \pm 0,29	5,2 \pm 0,31	4,8 \pm 0,42	4,7 \pm 0,46	4,1 \pm 0,21
Parenchyma, sm	1,6 \pm 0,06	1,9 \pm 0,13	1,8 \pm 0,14	1,7 \pm 0,11	1,5 \pm 0,15	1,1 \pm 0,1
Cortex	0,71 \pm -	0,89 \pm 0,6	0,84 \pm 0,04	0,81 \pm 0,03	0,68 \pm 0,08	0,48 \pm 0,08
Section of the pyramid, см ²	0,46 \pm 0,04	0,62 \pm 0,62	0,58 \pm 0,06	0,59 \pm 0,03	0,42 \pm 0,02	0,31 \pm 0,03

Note: The reliability of the differences with the control group is $p < 0.01$.

In the fifth stage of chronic kidney failure, the results of ultrasound examinations are combined and complement the developed manifestations of kidney failure, high azotemia, acid-base imbalance, electrolyte disturbances, anemia, and persistent hypertension. The following results compare the functional indicators of the kidneys, including the glomerular filtration rate

(GFR), tubular reabsorption, serum creatinine levels, and biometric kidney measurements at different stages of CKD, developed as a result of chronic diffuse glomerulonephritis.

A comparison of ultrasound results with clinical and functional indicators of the kidneys confirms the presence of pronounced signs of chronic kidney failure in stage 4 of CKD. There is a significant decrease in the glomerular filtration rate (GFR: 22.4 ± 6.2 ml/min), an increase in creatinine levels (368.4 ± 21.8 ml/min), a rise in the frequency of hypertension, and the appearance of anemia. These findings indicate the necessity of using a complex of active conservative treatment methods aimed at correcting the pathogenesis, ensuring a cardio-nephroprotective effect, and improving the anemic condition.

In the terminal stage of chronic kidney disease, the ultrasound results confirm the noticeable decrease in linear and volumetric kidney sizes. These data provide reliable evidence of nephrosclerosis. Furthermore, the ultrasound findings are combined and complement the severe manifestations of kidney failure, including high azotemia, acid-base imbalance, electrolyte disturbances, anemia, and stable hypertension.

Conclusions. Thus, in conclusion, the study of biometric kidney sizes highlights the most important features of the obtained data. The ultrasound results allow us to observe the dynamics of kidney biometric sizes at different stages of CKD. In stages 1 and 2 of CKD, with preserved excretory function, the biometric sizes increase. This is related to the pathogenetic mechanisms of chronic glomerulonephritis (CG) and CKD, as well as the activity of the immune-inflammatory process, hyperfiltration, and hyperperfusion of the parenchymal layer. With the progression of CKD, starting from stage 3C, and especially stage 3B, the biometric sizes of the kidneys tend to decrease. In stages 4 and especially in stage 5 of CKD, there is a statistically significant decrease in kidney biometric sizes. The dynamics of biometric sizes generally correlate with changes in the thickness of the parenchymal and cortical layers of the kidneys.

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